

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Abbas**FIRST NAME:** Tanveer**PROGRAM CODE:** DDIA**COURSE CODE:** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 1**INSTRUCTOR:** Dr. Gulma

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did not use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is 3 %

The author used the following software (e.g., MSWord 2016 Professional Plus on Windows 11 Home)

Seven key concepts:

1. Essay writing (EUCLID 2021, 6-12)
2. Thumb rules for writing papers (EUCLID 2021, 12-14)
3. Punctuations and use of commas (EUCLID 2021, 15-23)
4. Style guide (EUCLID 2021, 40-42)
5. American vs. British English (EUCLID 2021, 24-32)
6. Latin Abbreviations (EUCLID 2021, 58-61)
7. Conclusion (EUCLID 2021, 10-11)

WRITING GOOD ACADEMIC AND PROFESSIONAL PAPERS

1) INTRODUCTION

Doctorate studies from Euclid University begin with ACA-401D, which primarily focuses on basic skills of good essay writing. The study package covers the entire range of rules followed in all types of writing, especially essay writing. It highlights the importance of punctuation rules, including comma use, plagiarism, American vs. British English, Chicago page formats, and rules of thumb for writing papers and drafting conclusions. In this response paper, I will highlight basic rules and techniques for writing a paper following International standards.

2) ESSAY WRITING

Essay writing is the art of organizing and communicating your thoughts, ideas, and views. Essay writing seems to be a very simple subject, but it is not. Every essay must have a thesis statement around which the subject will remain focused. All efforts will be made to support the thesis statement by answering all relevant questions with data from authentic

sources. It is a gradual process interconnected with various stages of gathering information, thinking, reading, organizing, drafting, and redrafting. As a very initial step, we must know that we should start our assignment as soon as possible by defining questions, analyzing tasks, and preparing an initial draft.

After preparing an initial plan, we must enhance our focus on what to write through reading and researching. Reading and researching will give the knowledge and evidence to develop a thesis and answer (EUCLID 2021, 8). The process helps increase the breadth of knowledge and introduce more dynamics to the subject. During this process, the most essential thing to carry out is making notes of points relevant to the topic/argument (EUCLID 2021, 8).

After conducting detailed research on the topic, the next step is to organize the ideas into an answer. This may further develop the topic/argument or alter the initial essay plan. The vital thing to note here is that the essay should be balanced, including the evidence agreeing with the topic/argument and different or opposing views. The initial draft of the essay would highlight areas for improvement in the structure and framework of the paper. The structure consists of an introduction, body, and conclusion. The introduction mainly introduces the topic/argument to the reader and provides a roadmap to him. The body of an essay consists of paragraphs. Each is a building block in constructing your argument (EUCLID 2021, 10). Each section should contain a topic sentence, supporting sentences, evidence, and analysis. The conclusion typically summarizes the topic/argument in generalized terms. An important point is that a conclusion should never introduce a new topic or information (EUCLID 2021, 10).

The most critical step in essay writing is referencing the essay. The writings must be referenced to guard against plagiarism, a serious academic offense (EUCLID 2021, 11). There are many referencing styles to choose from. The referencing style should be indicated and applied consistently throughout the document. Referencing, apart from giving due credit to the author of the original idea/argument, also highlights the writer's analysis and skills of writing.

Lastly, the process concludes by editing the essay for corrections or additions. The editing process dramatically improves the quality of the content. Consider putting your writing aside for a few days and rereading your draft for editing. The said practice will introduce new and innovative additions to writing (EUCLID 2021, 11).

3) THUMB RULES FOR WRITING A PAPER

While writing a paper, some rules of thumb, if followed, will make the paper attractive, simple, and convenient for you to draft quickly. The basic rule is to state your paper's central thesis/ idea/ argument in the opening paragraph or at the start of the paper. While writing, stay focused on the main subject and avoid distractions, generic statements, and raising unnecessary suspicions.

Adopt a simple method of writing while avoiding high-sounding words, long strings of prepositional clauses, and plagiarism. Maintain a logical flow using punctuation, small sentences, and support assertions. Always remember that the reader's time is very important, and reading your paper should not be considered a waste of time. Make your writing exciting, thought-provoking, and enjoyable to read.

Plagiarism comes in two forms, both unacceptable. First, you plagiarize when you use the words of a source without quotation marks. Second, you plagiarize if you take ideas from a source without footnoting the source (EUCLID 2021, 14).

When you attribute views to the person whose ideas you are addressing, indicate the evidence for the attribution by noting relevant passages. But you need not include quotations. They should only be included if it is a dire necessity but avoid using too many of them (EUCLID 2021, 13). Finally, always take the views of scholars you are using very seriously and give due respect to their scholarly contributions. The key is to analyze rather than criticize their point of view. Once you finish your writing, try reading your paper out loud. Writing that does not sound right will not read right (EUCLID 2021, 14).

4) PUNCTUATION AND USE OF COMMA

To develop a logical, sequential, and coherent paper, punctuation is considered one of the most critical factors in writing. The set of punctuations, if used aptly, will add a logical flow to your paper and help you add finesse to your article without increasing the text. Amongst all punctuations, the most important is using a comma, which brackets non-restrictive phrases at the end of an introductory phrase, listing down more than two items, joining two independent clauses, etc. The use of an apostrophe is another essential facet of academic writing. There are some rules governing its usage. An apostrophe mainly indicates possession and shows that the letter has been omitted.

According to coursepack, “We must use ’s after singular nouns, plural nouns that do not end in s, and indefinite pronouns use ’ after plural nouns ending in s. In compound nouns where multiple nouns are linked to make one concept, place the apostrophe at the end of the final part (and match it to that noun).”

There has always been a point of discontent about where to put a period while using quotation marks. The American grammarian agreed that the period should always go inside the quotation marks. An essential point about comma usage is that it should be used after all listed items except the last. Note that there is no comma between the penultimate item in a list and ‘and’/‘or,’ unless required to prevent ambiguity – this is sometimes referred to as the ‘Oxford comma.’ however, always insert a comma in this position if it would help prevent confusion (EUCLID 2021, 20).

5) STYLE GUIDE

Some guidelines must be followed to adopt consistency in writing and bring similarity in the writing of different writers of the same organization while avoiding personal styles. EUCLID recommends the Chicago Rules (Turabian) and using American English. The style can have various formats and may include the layout of the paper, use of size and type of font, paragraph numbering, use of headings, sentence construction, abbreviations, symbols and terminologies, etc.

6) USA VS. UK ENGLISH

American English is considered the most influential language in the world because of its culture, history, solid political system, education system, and economy. Standard American English (SAE) and Standard British English (SBE) are the two variants of world English (EUCLID 2021, 25). The major difference is in their pronunciation. Some words have the same spelling but are pronounced differently, and vice versa. For example, in standard British English (SBE), the licence is written with ‘c,’ whereas, in standard American English (SAE), it is written with ‘s,’ i.e., license.

Likewise, both languages differ in the writing of dates. SBE follows the dd/mm/yy format, whereas SAE follows the mm/dd/yy format. The most important difference between the two is the use of quotation marks. SBE uses ‘inverted commas,’ whereas “quotation marks” are used in SAE. Similarly, there is a difference in the usage of a period after the quotation marks/ inverted commas. SBE puts the period outside the inverted commas, whereas SAE puts the period inside quotation marks.

7) LATIN ABBREVIATIONS

Latin abbreviations are appropriate in footnotes, bibliographies, and informal writing (e.g., information in parentheses). In business, formal, and technical writing, use the English equivalent of the abbreviation to avoid misinterpretation by readers (EUCLID 2021, 59-61). The most common Latin abbreviations in daily use are, e.g., i.e., etc., ibid, i.e., vs., etc.

8) CONCLUSION

The EUCLID study material provides a complete and comprehensive guideline for writing a paper. The response paper mainly included topics that were relatively new to me or were essential building blocks of a paper. It assisted me in every aspect of writing, from developing a thinking process to writing an introduction, main body, and conclusion. It also introduced me to punctuation, the Chicago Manual of Style (CMS), and the difference between SBE and SAE, which are considered critical for writing any paper. The study material was by far the most rewarding one for me.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth edition. Bangui: Euclid University.

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